

RESEARCH ARTICLE**CLADOCERANS: BIOINDICATORS OF THE EUTROPHICATION OF RAILWAY STATION POND AT GONDIA, DISTT. GONDIA, MAHARASHTRA****Wasudha J. Meshram**

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Abstract:

To study the cladocerans as bioindicators of the eutrophication, the physico-chemical parameters of Railway Station Pond were analysed seasonally from June 2006 to May 2007. Water temperature, transparency, pH, Dissolved oxygen, free Carbon dioxide, Alkalinity, Total hardness, Chlorides, Nitrates, Phosphates, BOD, COD. Cladocerans were recorded as 1410 ind/lit during the study period. The study reveals that the pond water is highly polluted which is leading to the stage of eutrophication due to the unplanned urbanizations, disposals of solid wastes and anthropogenic activities by the nearby people. However, there is an urgent need of an action for conservation and to reduce pollution level before it becomes unmanageable.

Keywords: Cladocerans, Bioindicators, Eutrophication, Railway Station Pond.

Introduction:

Cladocera is an ancient group of Paleozoic origin, occurring in all the types of water bodies such as lakes, ponds, and reservoirs etc inhabit pelagic, littoral and benthic zones. The Cladocera is an order which includes small crustaceans commonly called water fleas. These utilize varieties of food items such as the detritus, bacteria, unicellular and multicellular phytoplankton and serve as an excellent food for fish. They are also used in aquaculture, large filter-feeding planktons. These animals as intermediate hosts of some parasites may potentially pose a threat to human health (Forro *et al.*, 2008). These play vital role in energy transfer from primary producer to secondary consumer in aquatic ecosystem (Vijaykumar, 1999). The cladocerans are very sensitive to changes in the water quality and acts as one of the important bioindicators of aquatic pollution.

Materials and Methods:

Railway Station Pond located at 21. 27' and 39.18" N and 80 11' and 11.67" E and is about 1022 ft. above the mean sea level (MSL) with an area of 0.09 sq. km. Water samples were collected on monthly

basis and studied in the laboratory. Physical parameters were studied according to Welch (1952) and Lind (1974) and chemical parameters were studied by using APHA (1975).

The investigations on physico-chemical and biological parameters were carried out during June 2006 to May 2007. Monthly water samples were collected and brought to the laboratory for further analysis. To check the water quality, physico-chemical parameters like temperature, transparency, p^H , dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide, chloride, hardness and nutrients like phosphates and nitrates, BOD and COD. (APHA, 1975). At the same time the plankton samples were collected by using standard nylon plankton net made by bolting silk no. 25 planktons were preserved in 4% and identified using (Edmondson 1959) and other standard manuals.

Observations and Results:

During the present investigation the physical parameters such as temperature, transparency and chemical parameters namely p^H , dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide, chlorine, hardness, alkalinity, phosphate and nitrates, BOD and COD. The abundance of cladocerans was studied from June 2006 to May 2007. Table no. 1 shows the seasonal variations of various physico-chemical parameters of Railway Station Pond during the study period.

Parameters like water temperature ($33\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), free carbon dioxide (6.59 mg/l), total alkalinity (255.91 mg/l), nitrates (3.54 mg/l) and phosphates (5.36 mg/l) were maximum during summer while transparency (14.76 cm), p^H (7.73), dissolved oxygen (5.46 mg/l), BOD (14.82 mg/l) and COD (102.71 mg/l) showed its peak in winter and total hardness (699.91 mg/l) and chloride (41.93 mg/l) were recorded maximum during monsoon season.

Table 1: Annual range, Seasonal variations in Physico-chemical Parameters of Railway Station Pond during 2006-2007.

Parameters	Range	Monsoon	Winter	Summer
Water Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	27-36	31.4 \pm 1.966	27.9 \pm 0.544	34.4 \pm 1.556
Transparency (cm)	10.5-17	12.25 \pm 0.901	15.63 \pm 1.192	11.25 \pm 0.559
p^H	7.1-8.4	7.5 \pm 0.339	8.3 \pm 0.111	7.42 \pm 0.227
Dissolved oxygen (mg/l)	2.8-6.0	4.03 \pm 0.576	5.4 \pm 0.651	3.55 \pm 0.763
Free Carbon dioxide (mg/l)	2.7-12.5	7.78 \pm 2.002	3.78 \pm 0.869	10.13 \pm 2.128
Total Alkalinity (mg/l)	180-371	258.25 \pm 32.057	240 \pm 19.039	336 \pm 25.95
Total Hardness (mg/l)	585-970	896.25 \pm 97.921	825 \pm 39.408	657 \pm 53.033
Chloride (mg/l)	30.4-79.48	69.95 \pm 8.878	55.76 \pm 9.983	34.22 \pm 3.364
Nitrate (mg/l)	2.90-4.25	3.9 \pm 2.094	3.09 \pm 0.128	4.02 \pm 0.228
Phosphate (mg/l)	4.70-10.2	7.55 \pm 1.433	5.18 \pm 0.415	8.64 \pm 1.16
Sulphates (mg/l)	38.2-95.5	64.97 \pm 11.687	52.45 \pm 10.511	84.52 \pm 7.860
BOD	6.5-25	12.03 \pm 2.835	22.19 \pm 2.508	10.27 \pm 0.242
COD	55.6-200	120.8 \pm 28.460	154.93 \pm 32.058	70.63 \pm 13.550

Total 4 species of cladocerans were recorded during the study period. The most diversified species was Moina spp. (363 ind/lit.), Cereodaphnia spp. (362 ind/lit.), Diaphanosoma spp. (385 ind/lit.), and Alona spp. (300 ind/lit.). Total population of Cladocerans was recorded as 1410 ind/lit.). Seasonal

population density of Cladocerans recorded its peak during winter (720 ind/lit.i.e 51.00 %), during summer (390 ind/lit. i.e 28%) while least during monsoon (300 ind/lit.i.e 21%).

Figure 1: Seasonal Abundance of Cladocera in Railway Station Pond during 2006-2007

Discussion:

The seasonal study of cladocerans diversity of Railway Station Pond showed the peak in density and diversity during winter indicating the influence of physico-chemical factors. In the present study, the nutrients such as nitrates, phosphates etc. were recorded in lower concentration while peak in pH and dissolved oxygen, BOD and COD during winter season which may result into the increased population of cladocerans during this season while lower population was recorded during summer and monsoon season. This minimum density during summer and monsoon season also recorded by Krishnamurthy (1965). He stated that *Moina micrura* appeared to be most common in eutrophic ponds. Murugan (1989) studied the population ecology and population dynamic of *Moina micrura*. Cladoceran diversity presumably due to important bio-ecological relationship between macrophytes and zooplankton and is in confirmity with Venkataraman *et al.* (2000); Proctar *et al.* (1967). The least diversity in Railway Station Pond might be due to predation pressure by fishes (Fernando, 1980 and Venkataraman, 1983).

Quadri and Yousuf (1980) investigated the influence of some physico-chemical factors on the seasonal abundance of Cladocera. The maximum population of Cladocera in winter may be attributed to favourable temperature and availability of abundant food in the form of bacteria, nanoplankton and suspended detritus. Jayabhaye *et al.* (2006) has also reported similar observations. Patil *et al.* (2008) has reported minimum Cladocerans during monsoon months and attributed to the low water temperature, dissolved oxygen, and transparency play an important role in controlling the diversity and density of Cladocera.

K. Siva Kumar (2001) has reported maximum number of Cladocerans species during winter than summer season. The smaller number of these species during summer might be attributed to the higher temperature, evaporation of water or might be due to the depletion of the important factors such as Dissolved oxygen. The reduction in the number of species may also be due to predation. Welch (1952) also reported quantitatively less plankton in tropical inland waters.

Conclusion:

Having a glimpse of observations on physico-chemical parameters, such as temperature, transparency, P^H, dissolved oxygen, free carbon dioxide; total alkalinity, total hardness, nitrates and

phosphates, BOD and COD have the direct impact on abundance of cladocerans which indicates the eutrophic condition of railway station pond. Occurrence of these bio indicator species at higher rate indicates the mesosaprobic nature of this pond in future.

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